

MARIA TUPANSY AND THE CENTRALITY OF THE FEMININE IN
THE AUTHORITY OF JOSÉ DE ANCHIETA'S ASSUMPTION DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10116604*Felipe de Assunção Soriano*¹.*Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul – PUCRS.**felipeassj@yahoo.com.br***ABSTRACT**

The existence of a mariology in José de Anchieta's theatrical writings is easily demonstrable, but, far from being tied to the archetypes of his dramaturgy, he inserted himself into indigenous cultures and customs in such a way that he was able to offer original forms. As a good theologian that he was, he carried out a deep and thorough process of inculturation of his experience throughout his life, making his allegory migrate from Mary, Mother of Jesus to “Maria Tupansy” from the village of Reritiba. This process of decolonizing your own experience is an important step that will make it possible, using theater and other catechetical instruments, to present “Maria Tupansy” from the Tupi matriarchy perspective. By resuming Father Manoel da Nóbrega's missionary project, he concludes his theatrical *corpus* by offering the Indians a new character built from the remnants of the “old women” tradition and evoking their authority in the social and political space. It will be on the Reritiba mission, with the document *when they took an image to Reritiba* (1590), that José de Anchieta will carry out several processes of decolonization and resignification of his marital experience, giving a political, pedagogical and religious role to his fictional character.

Keywords: Anchieta theater. Maria Tupansy. Welcomed in the villages. Feminine. Matriarchy.

Introduction

The Society of Jesus' criticism of the authority of the elderly Indian women, called “old women”, and the ordering role of the feminine in Tupinambá villages found a place in José de Anchieta's theatrical catechesis. The metamorphosis that took place in the matriarchal figure of the “old women” to “Maria Tupansy” in the play *When they took an image to Reritiba* (1590)

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far surpasses the way in which the poet constructs his first mariological presentation in the *Auto de Guarapari* (1585). The metamorphosis that the Mother of Jesus goes through in the Anchieta theater offers us a new allegory based on the singular role of the feminine in the villages, building a new archetype, that is, a sign of the transmission of culture, unity of the village's principals and a sign of the local authority to from the female figure. Our article aims to demonstrate how José de Anchieta constructs this presentation, conceiving “Maria Tupansy” as a woman, warrior and lady of the village.

1. The Auto da Assunção (1590) and the Mission of Reritiba

For the inauguration of the church in the village of Reritiba, José de Anchieta prepared a theatrical piece to enthrone an image of the Virgin Mary on August 15, 1590. Writing in Tupi (general language), José de Anchieta builds his presentation incorporating elements of the Tupinambá woman and popular tradition from the late medieval period. Because of its devotional aspects, the film *When they took an image to Reritiba* (1590) celebrates the presentation of Mary - the Mother of God (Tupansy) to the Indians of Brazil.

In response to the cooling of the indigenous work of the Society of Jesus, José de Anchieta began the mission of Reritiba, resuming the program outlined by Father Manoel da Nóbrega in the work *Dialogue of the Conversion of the Gentile* (1556-1557). The show itself confirms that in this mission the Society of Jesus achieved its best results, presenting “Maria Tupansy” as a path to overcoming conflicts and enmities between indigenous nations.

His previous experience with the *Auto de Guarapari* (1585) was the laboratory where José de Anchieta realized the original place that the feminine could occupy in his catechesis, because, even using the word “Tupansy” since his first show, that is, the *Universal Preaching* (1561), only with the *Auto When they took an image to Reritiba* (1590) this character stops being an allegory and becomes the archetype of the feminine and mother of the villagers in the Reritiba mission from the Tupi matriarchy.

When we talk about the Tupi matriarchy we are recognizing that in this figure rests a specific authority and command given to the feminine in the villages, as guardian of life and transmitter of culture (FERNANDES, 2016, p. 48). In the correspondence of the Society of Jesus, there is constant criticism of the female group of “old” Indian women, that is, the wives of the village leaders, because of the authority they exercise over the entire taba (NAVARRO, 1988, p. 45) . It is common to find references to his authority regarding wars, festivals (anthropophagy) and adherence to baptism (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 255, v. 12).

Strictly speaking, the Company's interference in the practice of anthropophagy constituted a death blow to the authority of the “old women”, removing the centrality of the feminine in the life of the villages, as men were not attached to the practice of eating the flesh of their enemies, but, yes, to the fact of solemnly killing them. In fact, the interference of the Jesuits in the institution of “old women” (witch Indians), in the dissolution of *malocas* and in the practice of uxorilocality (female practice of receiving their husbands in their home and among their relatives – perpetuation of matriarchy), among others, It was a death blow to the place of command held by women in the villages (FERNANDES, 2016, p. 327).

Even though the Virgin does not speak, as biblical tradition predicts, José de Anchieta builds a deep dialogue in the show between his character and the Indians of Reritiba. In this way, all elements born and introduced into the village are referred to the authority of his character. Everything we know about his action comes from his interlocutors who state the reason for his visit, as the Indians receive this image as if it were a real person (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 251, vv. 1-5).

Unlike the *Auto de Guarapari* (1585), his mariology is condensed giving subjectivity to his character who, from the Tupi matriarchy, is presented with the authority of the wives of the village principals. Unlike the *Auto de Guarapari* (1585), here the indigenous people are not asked to submit to the priest and the doctrine, as these elements are already given in the figure of “Maria Tupansy”. Its originality surprises the public by adopting as a scheme the rite of welcome in the villages, giving the Virgin Mary its own protagonism and an organizing role in the show.

2. The “tearful salute” as a script in the *Auto da Assunção*

There is a unique custom among the Indians on the South Atlantic coast, which occurs on the Brazilian coast and also in the region of Uruguay and Paraguay called the “tearful salute”. It is believed that the ethnologist Pero Lopes de Souza was the first European to witness the fact, when on a two-month cruise along the mouth of the River Plate among the Charrúas Indians he recorded the fact. According to the report, when they disembarked in the Santa Maria region, they were received by the Indians with crying and sad songs (CARVALHO, 1903, p. 755).

The same is true of the Frenchmen Jean Léry and André Thevet, the Portuguese Gabriel Soares de Souza, Fernão Cardim and Simão de Vasconcelos about the Tupis of São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, Minas Gerais and Bahia. About this practice, Jean Léry offers us a detailed drawing:

The women of the family played the main role in the ceremony. When a foreigner or even an individual from one's own tribe approached a hut as a visitor, they made him sit in a hammock, the naked women squatted down in tears due to the dangers and labor they endured on the journey and offered him all sorts of congratulations. Custom demanded that people greeted in this way also cry, or when as a European he didn't have tears always ready, he at least pretended. These howls persisted until, according to Gabriel Soares, it became boring for them and they ordered the women to stop crying. The same author reported some particularities of the howling ceremony, and only after having strictly observed it did they bring food to the guest (CARVALHO, 1903, p. 756).

The first Portuguese were unable to understand the meaning of this unusual practice of the indigenous people of South America, a fact recorded only by some castaways who thought it was a sign of the guilt that the indigenous people had or of the terror that the white man imposed on them or, even, as a sign and I appeal to compassion for the fear of dying. Only later would Europeans be able to understand its true meaning, leaving us with few written references to this unusual practice.

These variants that touch on the central place that the feminine occupies in the life of the villages, José de Anchieta finds in the “tearful greeting” a safe way to consolidate the missionary work, placing, through “Maria Tupansy”, his Son Jesus-Tupã as the main one of the village . According to Tupi myths, where the “old” indigenous goddess, the Mother of Tupã , lives , her Son also lives. By placing the Virgin Mary at the head of *Tupãoca* [Church] (MÉTRAUX, 1590, p. 113), José de Anchieta presents Jesus- Tupã as its main one in that it presents Mary in the role of wife and mother (authority figure). José de Anchieta will be one of those few Europeans who will understand its meaning, even incorporating the “tearful salute” into his theatrical catechesis. Therefore, when we talk about a “tearful greeting” as a rite of welcome in Tupi villages, we must follow these five steps:

1. The visitor is received at the village landmark and taken to the house of a principal (chief);
2. The wives of the village leader are the ones who initiate the “tearful greeting”;
3. The guest must respond with tears to the greeting and without any words;
4. When the crying ends, a dialogue begins asking the reason for the visit;
5. Finally, something to eat is offered to strengthen the guest who arrived tired.

According to the account above, the wives of the village principal (old Indian women) perform the rite of welcome. This prerogative confers authority over her house and constitutes the feminine as a place for everything that concerns the social order. By taking the rite of welcome as a fundamental structure for the show, José de Anchieta gives the Virgin Mary the

main prerogatives of the Tupinambá woman, as it will be up to “Tupansy” to carry out the various stages of the Tupi rite while remaining open to her Son and in a dynamic of welcome to the indigenous people of the mission.

José de Anchieta realized the particular contribution that the feminine could offer to catechesis, leaving a clear record in some of the letters from Brazil. However, his ability was to codify the Christian tradition so that the indigenous people could recognize their hierarchical worldview in the Christian order of the spectacle. Therefore, as Tupi women walk ahead of their husbands in battles, this is how José de Anchieta presents his character as a mother, wife, lady of the village (ANCHIETA, 1984, p. 72).

3. The Auto da Assunção and the centrality of the feminine in the village.

The document *when they took an image to Reritiba* (1590) is also divided into five parts, that is, five sub-poems, with the only point of integration being the figure of “Maria Tupansy” and the Indians of the Reritiba mission (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 248). As the Virgin advances in the different paintings, her presentation advances in order to create an open and dynamic show. By singing “the death of Mary” in the opening, a more medieval expression for the Feast of the Assumption of Mary, José de Anchieta wishes to celebrate her life (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 249, vv. 1-4). By insisting on her motherhood and virginity, he establishes a new bond with the Indians who accept Christian baptism, presenting “Maria Tupansy” as the one who goes ahead of us, guiding us towards life.

The image of the Virgin Mary is brought by boat to the village and received by a choir of *curumins* (Children) who sing their great day (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 249, vv. 5-9). The poem presents the Virgin crying “anxious for heaven”, that is, eager to meet her beloved Son, because where we find devotion and piety, the Virgin's Tupi identity is hidden, in this case, the “tearful greeting” (CARDOSO, 1977, pp. 249-251, vv. 25-28). This reference produces a scenic inversion that surprises its audience, as it transforms the Virgin from guest to host when we see her unique presidency in the Tupi rite. Such creativity confesses that the Virgin is the daughter of the people of the land, wife of the village's principal and the indigenous people of that mission are her guests.

According to the reception rite, when the guest is received outside the house of a principal, as is the case in the case when *they took an image to Reritiba* (1590), he is led by a delegation. As etiquette dictates, the Indians should say nothing while the Virgin weeps, but

simply lament so as not to be ungrateful. This tension between arrival and departure keeps the first hymn open and gives the show an eschatological dynamic.

Great happy day
It emerges for us today:
Rejoice all of you
With the death of Mary.
She goes with joy
To heaven, your luck:
Chase away our death
And for life guides us. (...)
All anxious for heaven,
You cried continually:
You live very happily today
next to your Son.
Guide her quickly and safely
Follow your step forward.
I hope that without delay
Your sweetness invades me
(CARDOSO, 1977, p. 249).

According to the Anchieta scheme, the presence of the Virgin Mary in the village means the arrival of the Kingdom of God to the Indians. This fact puts in check the evil forces represented by the demons, who until then are the owners of the village. As the enthronement of the image constitutes a new foundation for the mission, José de Anchieta places a guardian angel for the village of Reritiba (European scheme). He is the one who summons the Indians to the Churchyard, the Principal's house, the stage for the expulsion of demons. The movement up from the village port to the churchyard already anticipates the theological meaning of the assumption of the village that welcomes the Gospel (Good news).

In the second act we are faced with the dialogue that the host has had since the guest's last visit, according to the Tupi welcome rite. Demons are a sign of what needs to be overcome and which compromises conversion, namely, "illness, fever, dysentery, corruption and anxiety, so that the community believes in God, your son and guide" (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 251). It is the custodian angel, or rather, the guardian angel, who expel them, so that the Mother of the King can enter the village of Reritiba (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 249-252).

Angel: Mother of God, Virgin Mary,
Come visit the village,
The devil will be cast out of her.
I hope with joy
Let us progress in loving you!
Guardian angel of the village,
I will expel you from it,
And the Mother of the King will enter!...
I'm going to attack you now, hey!

Demon: Oh, poor me! With fight

The Mother of God freed
Land that evil gave me...
Mother of God, my enemy!
(CARDOSO, 1977, p. 252)

The figures of demons play a particular role in the Anchieta records, as they are the ones who accuse the indigenous and Portuguese people by bringing the matter to correct customs. It is no coincidence that these figures always appear disguised as a comical representation, which aims to capture the public's attention, encouraging satire and ridicule (FREYRE, 2004, p. 200). José de Anchieta uses them in his drama, because, even trying to sabotage the work of Creation, they appear as “servants of God” to punish men (VIEIRA, 1965, p. 295).

The dialogue between guest and host continues in the third act of the show. Now, with dances, the Indians already catechized with the *matachins* (popular dances from Portugal with warrior movements) speak. In these verses we find the request that the village makes to the Virgin: that she come and teach my people to follow your path, that she come to bring conversion, which is to come closer to the Real God and accept the blessed law (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 253). The indigenous people newly arrived in the village also respond with dance, who parade in their own way, because, with even greater humility, they know who they should turn to [Matriarchy] (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 254).

In the fourth act, where we find the greatest climax, the leaders of the nations speak to the Virgin. According to the scheme adopted by José de Anchieta, three chiefs speak: an Indian from the north (Tupinambá) and another from the south (Paratiy), signaling that the Reritiba mission is a place of convergence for all the nations of Brazil. In these prayers, in response and gratitude, dressed in “joyful frenzy”, the Indian Paratiy speaks, promising to put an end to the joy of the “old women” [the practice of anthropophagy] (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 255).

We know that this fourth act takes place inside the Church (Principal's House), because of the information about the liturgical space that is offered to us by the speakers. It is the Reritiba Indian who says that he came from far away to hear mass and that there are paintings in the Church that are bewitching (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 255). However, the Virgin is unhappy to know that the Indians from the Reritiba village did not come to the reception, as they did not agree with the fact that there were so many Indians on their land. The conflicts and enmities between the Tupi nations still need to be overcome, a fact that worries the Indians themselves and scandalizes the Virgin Mary (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 256).

In the last part of the show, José de Anchieta concludes his presentation by going over Mary's life, as she was given to us as a sign of her Son's proximity as the village's leader (Jesus

Tupã). By evoking the Tupi matriarchy along the lines of the “tearful salute”, José de Anchieta presents his character under the prerogatives of the Tupinambá woman. She is a sign that reveals the power of God that defeats evil (Anhangá), because, as José de Anchieta says, He created her to be the Mother of Jesus-Tupã, the *immortal* Lord of existence.

In the apotheosis of the show, our character is finally named and proclaimed as lady of the village, as in unison the entire village proclaims her “chosen woman”, one who has been magnified with the goods of grace, being the most beautiful of the Tupinambá women. José de Anchieta is the one who insists that by becoming a mother, that is, by giving her “yes” to the work of redemption, she brings the power to defeat evil (Anhangá), as a daughter of God and our sister in his Son (CARDOSO , 1977, p. 257).

Out of great love for us sinners
Tupã made an excellent saint,
The most beautiful of all our people
And everyone enriched her with the best gifts.

Saying “be my dear mother”,
He made her chosen among every woman,
He magnified her with perfect affection,
And he filled his life with great blessings.

In it, Tupã embodies, like a boy,
And he was born of a Virgin. To be removed
Our miseries, come visit us
Wanting to be a cute little one
(CARDOSO, 1977, p. 257-258).

In this scheme, it is “Maria Tupansy” who welcomes us and introduces us to her Son (Principal of the village), as she is now the one who welcomes as her guests all the indigenous people of Brazil (Indians from the south - Paratiy and from the North - Tupinambá). In this scheme, the show insists that the Indian's place is in the village, as they now leave the jungles and forests to see the reception being placed under their command and authority, that is, who teaches the ways, who brings conversion, who brings us closer to God, who shelters the blessed in his goodness, freeing us from evil (CARDOSO, 1977, p. 253).

Final considerations

The auto *when they took an image to Reritiba* (1590) is a mature work by José de Anchieta, where he deepens and refines his catechetical instruments, proposing a metamorphosis in his allegories. By taking the “tearful greeting” as a scheme for his theatrical

catechesis, José de Anchieta reaches us with something new that highlights the depth of this unusual practice of the Tupi and the relevance of his female character. Its opening is felt in the action of “Maria Tupansy” and in the response of the Indians gathered for the feast, giving a particular role to the feminine that was rejected in the first hour of the catechesis.

Even though it is an indirect relationship, due to the influence of the biblical scheme (woman without a word), it seems plausible to see “Maria Tupansy” presiding over every moment of the show. First, because of the place that our character occupies as “wife of the principal” (Place of authority) and, second, because she occupies the role of “Mother” of Jesus in the allegory. However, the silence of “Maria Tupansy” is her distinctive mark, as it is not a silence of submission but rather a sign of her authority that reveals her leading role in the show.

According to the scheme developed by José de Anchieta, Maria will play a well-defined pedagogical role, attracting and leading the Indians to the Gospel. Unlike the *Auto de Guarapari* (1585), where the Indian is asked to submit to the priests, in the auto *when they took an image to Reritiba* (1590) the missionaries are not even mentioned, except in a prayer for a sick priest, conferring the mission of catechist your character. This authority of the “old women” in catechesis also appears in other correspondences by José de Anchieta, highlighting his intention and confirming a particular place for “Tupansy” (ANCHIETA, 1984, p. 111).

Father Antônio Blázquez, writing in Bahia (1557), reports to his superiors how the “old women” exercise authority over the Indians, as they consult them whether or not they should go to war (NAVARRO, 1988, p. 185-186). Based on this logic, “Maria Tupansy” is placed as the balance, the one they must always turn to as mediator in overcoming conflicts between nations, always recording her name, or better yet, continually invoking her. The show's scheme confirms the catechetical project of Father Manuel da Nóbrega, in the *Dialogue of the Conversion of Gentil* (1556-1557), which reaches its peak when José de Anchieta presents “Maria Tupansy” as a path to pacification.

As the transmission of culture and values necessarily passes through the female role in the villages, it becomes plausible to consider the ordering role given to her character. According to the scheme, the feminine is also a link of incorporation into village life. When presenting “Maria Tupansy” all the elements born or incorporated into the village only have meaning when linked to her craft. In the text of the show, this relationship is reinforced again when the village's leaders direct their chorus (speech) to the image of “Tupansy”, promising in praise of the visit to embrace their law, their way.

In the same way that theater expands the use of the Catechism (1988) and its application, its strategies are narrowed and its methods are refined. Such decolonization of her own marital

experience is the best result of her cultural insertion. Although the fact of teaching the Catholic faith in itself already constitutes a colonial action, his Mariology was capable of profound displacement, opening space for new power relations. José de Anchieta was able to identify the sociocultural pattern of the village people, covering their value systems, way of living, thinking, speaking and their collective expressions. Through symbols and rites, he adapted his worldview marked by deities and spirits to the Judeo-Christian tradition, i. is, in order to conceive a new symbolic code based on the warrior imaginary in which the Indian was forged.

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